

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS, WITH REFERENCE TO MULTI DIMENSIONAL POVERTY INDEX OF INDIA

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Abstract:

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a group of seventeen interlinked global goals which are a blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for everyone. These were set up in 2015 by the United Nations General Assembly (UN-GA) and are projected to be achieved by the year 2030. The SDG Vertical, and the various Ministries are the nodal agency for SDGs in India. This paper tries to look into important aspects of Multi dimensional Poverty index in India as the NITI Aayog is using a very good methodology to understand the deprivation of people due to poverty. Poverty eradication is very important as it goes hand in hand with upliftment of human society and also impact other SDG goals like health well-being, zero hunger, economic growth, sustainable economic progress and Peace.

Keywords: *NITI Aayog, Multi-dimensional Poverty Index, Poverty, Sustainable Development Goals.*

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Introduction

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are in the form of 17 interlinked global goals designed to be a blueprint to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all. The SDGs were set up in 2015 by the United Nations General Assembly (UN-GA) and are projected to be achieved by the year 2030. They are included in an UN-GA Resolution known as Agenda 2030. The SDGs were developed as the framework to succeed the Millennium Development Goals which ended in 2015. On 25th September 2015, 193 countries of the United Nations General Assembly adopted the 2030 Development Agenda titled Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

The 17 Sustainable Development Goals are:

1. No Poverty,
2. Zero Hunger,
3. Good Health and Well-being,
4. Quality Education,
5. Gender Equality,
6. Clean Water and Sanitation,
7. Affordable and Clean Energy,
8. Decent Work and Economic Growth,
9. Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure,
10. Reducing Inequality,
11. Sustainable Cities and Communities,
12. Responsible Consumption and Production,
13. Climate Action,
14. Life Below Water,
15. Life On Land,
16. Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions,
17. Partnerships for the Goals.

These goals are to be achieved as per the time frame. This study is going to take into account the important goals of SDGs of poverty eradication by understanding the multi dimensional poverty index in India.

Objectives of the study

1. To understand Sustainable Development Goals
2. To understand India's role in achievement of SDGs.
3. To understand India's multidimensional poverty index
4. To give suitable suggestions.

Research Methodology

This study is going to rely on secondary data and which will be available from various reports of government, NITI Aayog, United Nations and similar reports.

Data Sources

Since the study is based on secondary data only, data will be collected from various Indian government websites, NITI Aayog reports, United nations Development Programme Reports and their websites including journals and articles.

Limitations of the study

The study does not feature primary data, which could have given a different dimension to this study.

Sustainable Development Goals

On 6th July 2017, the SDGs were made more actionable by United Nations Resolution adopted by the General Assembly. The resolution identified specific targets for each goal, along with indicators that are used to measure improvement toward each target. The year by which the target is meant to be achieved is between 2020 and 2030. For some of the targets, no end date is mentioned.

To facilitate monitoring, a variety of tools exist to track and visualize progress towards the goals. For example, the online publication SDG Tracker, launched in June 2018, presents available data across all indicators. The SDGs pays attention to multiple issues, like gender equity, education, and culture. There were serious impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on all 17 SDGs in the year 2020.

Zero Poverty in India as one of the Goal

The Multidimensional Poverty Index (MPI) has been used by the United Nations Development Programme in its (HRD) Human Development Report since 2010. India has developed National Multidimensional Poverty Index (NMPI). Target 1.2. of this goal refers to reducing “at least by half the proportion of men, women and children of all ages living in poverty in all its dimensions according to national definitions.

A national MPI is a headline statistic of: To compare poverty across subnational regions, to track poverty over time, to highlight how poor are the people in poverty, using direct information from the set of MPI indicators. National MPIs are always reported along with several in-built statistics that show the level of poverty by indicator. multidimensionally poor person suffers from. The national MPI is constructed directly from each person’s profile of deprivations across each indicator, built from a single household survey that captures the data

on all the indicators.

Table Number 1

Headcount Ratio The size of the bar represents the percentage of population who are multidimensionally poor in each State/UT of India for the year 2015-16.

State/Union Territory	Percentage of population who are multidimensionally poor
Bihar	51.91 %
Jharkhand	42.16 %
Uttar Pradesh	37.79 %
Madhya Pradesh	36.65 %
Meghalaya	32.67 %
Assam	32.67 %
Chhattisgarh	29.91%
Rajasthan	29.46%
Odisha	29.35%
Nagaland	25.23%
Arunachal Pradesh	24.27%
West Bengal	21.43%
Gujarat	18.60%
Manipur	17.89%
Uttarakhand	17.72%
Tripura	16.65%
Maharashtra	14.85%
Telangana	13.74%
Karnataka	13.16%
Andhra Pradesh	12.31%
Haryana	12.28%
Mizoram	9.80%
Himachal Pradesh	7.62%
Punjab	5.59%
Tamil Nadu	4.89%
Sikkim	3.82%
Goa	3.76%
Kerala	0.71%
Dadra & Nagar Haveli	27.36%
Jammu & Kashmir and Ladakh	12.58%
Daman & Diu	6.82%

Chandigarh	5.97%
Delhi	4.79%
Andaman & Nicobar Islands	4.30%
Lakshwadeep	1.82%
Puducherry	1.72%

Source: https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2021-11/National_MPI_India-11242021.pdf

The above table number 1 shows State of Bihar shows the highest multidimensionally poor with figure of 51.91 %, and Union territory of Puducherry showing the least multidimensionally poor with figure of 1.72%.

The India's MPI has three equally weighted dimensions – health, education, and standard of living. Weights are assigned to each dimension then sub weights to all the indicators.

Table 2 Indicators in India's NMPI Model

Dimension	Weights	Indicator	Deprived if
Health	1/3	Nutrition	An household is measured as deprived if any child between the ages of 0 to 59 months, or woman between the ages of 15 to 49 years, or man between the ages of 15 to 54 years -for whom nutritional information is available is found to be undernourished.
		Child & Adolescent	An child under 18 years of age has died in the family in the five-year period preceding the survey.
		Mortality	An household is considered deprived if any woman in the household who has given birth in the 5 years preceding the survey, has not received at least 4 antenatal care visits for the most recent birth, or has not received assistance from trained skilled medical personnel during the most recent childbirth.
Education	1/3	Years of Schooling	Not even one member of the household aged 10 years or older has completed six years of schooling.
		School Attendance	Any school-aged child is not attending school up to the age at which he/she would complete class 8.

Standard of Living	1/3	Cooking Fuel	A household cooks with dung, agricultural crops, shrubs, wood, charcoal or coal.
		Sanitation	The household has unimproved or no sanitation facility or it is improved but shared with other households.
		Drinking Water	The household does not have access to improved drinking water or safe drinking water is at a minimum round trip of 30-minute walk from home.
		Electricity	The household has no electricity
		Housing	The household has inadequate housing: the floor is made of natural materials, or the roof or wall are made of rudimentary materials.
		Assets	The household does not own more than one of these assets: radio, TV, telephone, computer, animal cart, bicycle, motorbike, or refrigerator; and does not own a car or truck.
		Bank Account	No household member has a bank account or a post office account.

Source: [https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2021-11/National MPI India-11242021.pdf](https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2021-11/National_MPI_India-11242021.pdf)

Table number 2 above shows the India's Multi Poverty Index by showing the various dimension, weights, indicators and who is considered as deprived person.

The Alkire-Foster Method

The Alkire-Foster (AF) method is a way of measuring multidimensional poverty developed by OPHI's Sabina Alkire and James Foster. Using the Foster-Greer-Thorbecke poverty measures, it involves counting the different types of deprivation that individuals experience at the same time, such as a lack of education or employment, or poor health or living standards. These deprivation profiles are analysed to identify who is poor, and then used to construct a multidimensional index of poverty (MPI).

Way Ahead

This baseline National MPI Report is a milestone and a first step in bringing multidimensional poverty as a tool to the policy table at the national and state levels in India. It is expected that the report will play an instrumental role in sensitizing government, researchers, civil society,

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citizens, and other stakeholders on the need for and importance of MPI as a powerful policy instrument. At the higher levels, MPI could be used as an input to design development policies and schemes and budget allocations. At district levels, MPI can decide priority of execution and delivery.

Conclusion

The MPI is a broad indicator for understanding the issue related to poverty and deprivation. This method has given a new dimension to eradicate poverty in India as the available data gives the policy makers the right path to frame policies for the benefit of poor and deprived sections of the society. This field will also encourage more of research in this area.

References

- <https://www.niti.gov.in/verticals/sustainable-dev-goals#:~:text=The%20SDG%20framework%20specifically%20targets,plan%20to%20reduce%20multidimensional%20poverty.>
- <https://www.in.undp.org/content/india/en/home/our-focus.html>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sustainable_Development_Goals
- https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2021-08/NER_SDG_Index_NITI_26082021.pdf
- https://www.niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2021-11/National_MPI_India-11242021.pdf
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Multidimensional_Poverty_Index